

Impact monitoring Plan / D5.1

WP 5, T 5.1

Authors: Tommaso Giomi (ITeC), Álvaro Santana (SYM), Laura Reus (SOO), Subarna Sivashanmugam (TEE), Sergio Rodriguez (TEE), Jose Lucas (ITeC)

Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

1 Technical references

Project Acronym	RECONSTRUCT
Project Title	A Territorial Construction System for a Circular Low-Carbon Built Environment
GA number	101082265
Project Coordinator	Kathleen Blanco Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción de Cataluña Head of Innovation Project Management Department kblanco@itec.cat
Project Duration	June 2023 – May 2027 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D5.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 5 - Monitoring and assessment of impacts
Task	T5.1 - Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring
Lead beneficiary	1. ITeC
Contributing beneficiary/ies	4. SYM, 10. SOO, 15. TEE
Due date of deliverable	29 February 2024
Actual submission date	28 February 2024

* PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	15/02/2024	First internal draft (ITeC, SYM, SOO, TEE)	Tommaso Giomi (ITeC), Álvaro Santana (SYM), Laura Reus (SOO), Subarna Sivashanmugam (TEE), Sergio Rodriguez (TEE), Jose Lucas (ITeC)
2.0	22/02/2024	First external review (COM, ITeC)	Marcela Rubio (COM), Tommaso Giomi (ITeC)
2.1	27/02/2024	Second external review (GEP)	Jasper Sleuwaegen (GEP)
2.2	28/02/2024	Final version (ITeC)	Tommaso Giomi (ITeC)

List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AAC	Alkali Activated Cement
AACC	Alkali Activated Cement Concrete
AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
BIM	Building Information Model
BoM	Bill of Materials
BoQ	Bill of Quantities
CCC	Circular Construction Cluster
CDW	Construction Demolition Waste
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CMR VOC	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic and Reprotoxic Volatile Organic Compounds
COAC	Col·legi d'Arquitectes de Catalunya
COM	Comsa (partner)
DNHS	Do No Harm to the Environment principle
EPD	Environmental Product Declarations
EPBD	Energy Performance Building Directive
EU	European Union
EWC	European Waste classification
GHG	Green House Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GMA	Environmental Model Managing software
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HOL	Holland Composites (partner)
INC	Incasol (partner)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITeC	Instituto de Teconología de la Construcción de Catalunya (partner)
IVE	Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LEER	European Codes and Spanish standard
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis
MCDM	Multiple Criteria Decision Making
MCI	Material Circulator Indicator
OPC	Ordinary Portland Cement

RDF	Resource Description Framework
R&D	Research and Development
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SOO	Societat Organica (partner)
SYM	Symbiosis (partner)
TCQi	Time Cost Quality software
TEE	Teesside University (partner)
TRRC	Textile Reinforced Recycled Concrete
TVOC	Total Volatile Organic Compounds
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WLC	Whole Life Carbon
WP	Work Package

2 Table of contents

1	Technical references	2
2	Table of contents	6
3	Introduction	8
3.1	RECONSTRUCT: Goals and objectives	8
3.2	Monitoring and assessment of impacts	8
3.3	Output expected	9
4	Assessment plans.....	13
4.1	RECONSTRUCT assessments.....	13
4.2	EU frameworks	15
4.2.1	LEVEL(s)	16
4.2.2	Ellen MacArthur.....	18
4.2.3	RE10 tool.....	20
4.2.4	S-LCA guidelines by UNEP	22
5	LCA & LCC	23
5.1	Description.....	23
5.1.1	State of the art.....	25
5.1.2	Strengths and weaknesses	26
5.2	Partner's methodology.....	27
5.2.1	Input required	28
5.2.2	Output obtained.....	31
6	Circularity Assessment	33
6.1	Description.....	33
6.1.1	State of the art.....	35
6.1.2	Strengths and weaknesses	36
6.2	Methodology for the assessment.....	38
6.2.1	Output obtained.....	43
7	Social impact assessment	44
7.1	Description.....	44
7.1.1	State of the art.....	45
7.1.2	Strengths and weaknesses	45
7.2	Partner's methodology.....	46
7.2.1	Input(s) required and Output(s) obtained.....	48
8	Project Impact assessment.....	50
8.1	Description.....	50
8.1.1	State of the art.....	50

8.1.2	Strengths and weaknesses	50
8.2	Partner's methodology.....	51
8.2.1	Input required	51
8.2.2	Output obtained.....	51
9	Conclusions	53
9.1	Holistic management of project assessments.....	53
9.2	T5.1 – Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring : next steps....	54
10	References	55

List of Figures

Figure 4.1	RECONSTRUCT Gantt Chart.....	14
Figure 4.2	Level(s)' Indicators.....	17
Figure 4.3	Material flows considered to arrive at the Material Circularity Indicator of a product.	19
Figure 4.4	Table of results and evaluation criteria of R10 Tool.	21
Figure 4.5	Assessment system from categories to unit of measurement.	22
Figure 5.1	Three pillars of sustainability.....	23
Figure 5.2	The product life cycle stages. Extracted from a PRé Sustainability B.V. article	24
Figure 5.3	Four steps of life cycle assessment. Extracted from a PRé Sustainability B.V. article.....	24
Figure 6.1	Open and Closed loop (circular) of resources. Source: Societat Orgànica.....	34
Figure 6.2	Stages of lifecycle of a building to close the loop (green and blue stages). Source: Societat Orgànica	34
Figure 6.3	Outline of Synerplatform	41
Figure 7.1	Stakeholder category and its relationship with sub-categories with the RECONSTRUCT	47
Figure 9.1	– List of the inputs needed for each assessment.....	53

3 Introduction

3.1 RECONSTRUCT: Goals and objectives

RECONSTRUCT aims to develop low-carbon alternatives to Ordinary Portland Cement. These alternatives will be used in combination with recycled and bio-based materials to produce in-situ components, precast components, and sandwich panels. The components will be designed to be removable, repairable, and reusable.

The digitization of the entire lifecycle of construction materials will enable the tracking and sharing of material information. The extensive use of digital tools will support the design, construction, and deconstruction phases, thereby minimizing waste and its impact. These innovations will be applied to both onsite and prefabricated construction approaches. AI-based solutions will establish stable regional supply chains of waste materials.

RECONSTRUCT aims to demonstrate its approach by constructing two real-scale demonstrators and setting up regional Circular Construction Clusters that incorporate the entire local value chain. The project aims to achieve a significant reduction in material consumption and carbon footprint by reducing waste generated during construction by 90%, developing materials with up to 0% virgin content, reducing the carbon footprint of buildings by 50%, and increasing recycling to 90%.

3.2 Monitoring and assessment of impacts

The construction sector has a significant impact on the planet, accounting for 30% of natural resource extraction, 25% of solid waste generation, and 40% of greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, it is crucial to consider the environmental impact of future building solutions.

The importance of monitoring the performances of buildings, components and materials is widely recognised. RECONSTRUCT wants to push this investigation further with a long process of monitoring and evaluation of impact will be carried on throughout the whole duration of the project, to assess the if the project is developing products, demos and platform in line with the scope initially stated.

The goal is to monitor short-term and estimate mid and long-term impacts by assessing the demonstrators lifecycle performance using the data collected and digital tools.

To monitor the environmental, economic, and social impact of the RECONSTRUCT project, 4 assessments will be produced:

- Life Cycle Assessments & Life Cycle Costing,
- Circular Assessment
- Social Impact Assessment
- Project Impact Assessment

This document is where all the partners involved in the WP5, Monitoring and assessment of impacts, plan how to draft these 4 assessments.

The demonstrators object of performance evaluation will be the two demo buildings, but also the components produced for the building construction and materials created inside RECONSTRUCT. Each one of this demonstrators category will have their own characteristics that will need to be considered when assessing the impact, they have.

In recent years, the urge to tackle the climate crisis pushes legislators, companies, and researchers to consider the sustainability of the solutions studied.

The focus of much research is concentrated on the environmental impact of innovative solutions, but for an innovation to be implemented, the economic impact it will have on society can't be forgotten and how it will socially affect people's way of life, health and well-being.

This can be done by evaluating the environmental, economic and social impact that each factor will produce.

Comparing results from different outcomes is crucial to really understand the performance of materials, components, and building. To compare products produced with different technologies, in different geographical area, for different uses, one holistic framework is needed. A structure that defines what indexes must be measured, where and how to collect input data and how they must be elaborated.

Comparable results can be achieved only if achieved respecting some shared guidelines. The assessment that will be carried out in RECONSTRUCT will be tailored to comply with the frameworks, regulations and guidelines established in the market for every sector.

3.3 Output expected

RECONSTRUCT aims to mitigate the impact of buildings by producing materials with low CO2 emissions, incorporating bio-based materials, and utilizing industrial production waste. Additionally, the circularity of the construction elements in the two demonstrations, from design to end-of-life, will further reduce the overall impact of the buildings.

Some of the most relevant goals of the project are:

- Reduction of embodied CO2 by **80%** compared to a similar building with traditional technology.
- Recycled content in buildings above **90%** of the overall the lifecycle.
- Reduction of construction waste by **90%** compared to a similar building with traditional technology.
- Closed-loop CDW recycling increase between **30-50%** of the overall the lifecycle.
- Non-renewable content below **5%** of the overall the lifecycle.

The goal of WP5 “Monitoring and assessment of impacts” is clear: create a portfolio of documents that can exactly assess the impact of the RECONSTRUCT solution during their lifetime considering environmental, economic and social aspects. These

assessments will be replicable for other materials, components, and buildings, and they will be comparable to other similar assessments made respecting the same frameworks.

The project's digital tools will be populated with demonstrator data to calculate the circularity performance of buildings, components, and materials, as well as their short-term environmental and economic impacts.

Simulations using alternative design and usage parameters will allow for the estimation of long-term impacts based on scenarios regarding materials used, building design, component second life, and technological uptake. These projections will then be used to study the potential social impacts if circular construction is mainstreamed.

The WP5 comply with the RECONSTRUCT Objective 6: "Calculate RECONSTRUCT's current and future environmental, economic & social impacts" and his Key performance indicators (KPIs), that include Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) (10), Life Cycle Costing (LCCs) (10), Circularity assessments (5), and Scenarios (10).

The work in task 5.1 - Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring will produce this deliverable, D5.1 – Impact monitoring plan, and will continue monitoring the work done in the WP5 - Monitoring and assessment of impacts, and in other WPs, as explained in the last paragraph of this chapter.

Each task in WP5, after 5.1, will produce one assessment each.

- *Task 5.2 – Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing* will produce the *D5.2 – LCA & LCC studies*, with analysis of impact of the RECONSTRUCT products throughout all the life cycle phases. The expectations on how to structure the D5.2 are analysed in the chapter 5 – LCA & LCC of this document. Task leader: ITEC
- *Task 5.3 - Circularity Assessment & Symbiosis potential* it is divided in two subtasks:
 - T5.3.1 – Circularity assessment, which will give a value at the most important circularity indexes for the product of the RECONSTRUCT project
 - T5.3.2 – Symbiosis potential, which will evaluate the potential of the CDW, Construction and Demolition Waste materials, to be re-included in the construction value chain. Both subtasks will produce the *D5.3 – Circularity assessment*, explained in chapter 6 – Circularity assessment of this document. Task leader: SOO
- *Task 5.4 – Social Impact Assessment* will understand the social performance of the project, considering the impact on people's way of life, community, health, and wellbeing. It will produce the *D5.4 – Social impact assessment* which is explained in the chapter 7 – Social impact assessment of this document. Task leader: TEE
- *Task 5.5 – Conducting simulations to estimate future impacts* is a final assessment that will use the work done in the other assessments to create simulations of future impact of the product of RECONSTRUCT after the end of the project and some simulations with different scenarios (e.g.: creating the same product but using a different material, changing the architectural design of the buildings, etc.) .To do so, it will be needed an integration of the software used for every assessment and throughout the project, in order to easily have dynamic information from different sources. This task will carry out the work needed to produce *D5.5 – Project Impact*

Assessment, as listed in the chapter 8 – Social Impact Assessment of this document.
Task leader: TEE

The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive outline of how the various WP5 assessments are produced, to provide a consistent framework and to ensure consistency of economic, environmental, and social results.

It was crucial to begin planning the workflow needed to draft each assessment at an early stage, even if the tasks 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 related to the 3 “thematic” assessments will start from month 30 of the project (December 2025), and task 5.5 related to the “general” assessment in month 37 (July 2026).

Each Task Leader was involved in writing the relevant chapter of this document. TEE has been involved in this document, even though it was not initially foreseen in the grant agreement. All the partners involved in *WP5 – Monitoring and assessment of impacts* thought that it was important to start planning the whole package of assessments at an early stage, including the Social Impact Assessment and the final Project Impact Assessment, where TEE is the lead partner.

To plan the structure for the RECONSTRUCT’s assessment it is crucial that every partner of the *WP5 – Monitoring and assessment of impacts* analyses the EU frameworks related to the topics covered in each assessment.

Respecting these frameworks will give us the opportunity to have impact results that can be comparable with other results of projects assessed respecting the same format.

To be able to be comprising the results between different projects is crucial to understand the performance of new materials, products, and R&D solutions.

These frameworks must be respected to help identify the initial data required for each assessment and the calculation methodologies to be used.

By streamlining the initial information and development processes, it is possible to determine the common information needed for various assessments and whether outputs from one document are required as inputs for another.

This work aims to ensure homogeneity and harmonization in the information used within RECONSTRUCT.

A deeper focus on the frameworks needed for the RECONSTRUCT’s assessment is carried out in chapter 4 - Assessments plans, Paragraph 4.2 EU Frameworks of this document. The work needed for the harmonization of the information and data used in the *WP5 – Monitoring and assessment of impacts* will be carried on during next months in the *Task 5.1 – Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring*, as explained in chapter 9 – Conclusions of this document.

The monitoring plan will continue to be developed in the task *Task 5.1 - Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring*, ending in month 42, at which point, the three specific assessments of WP5, LCA and LCC, Circularity assessment and Social Assessment, will also be published.

The plan outlined in this document is published at month 9, however the planned solutions will be updated throughout the project, as it is necessary to connect with other parts of the

project, especially WP2, 3 and 4. There will be a constant monitoring of the work done in other WPs, to assure that the structure of the assessments can easily receive info from the inputs necessary.

The information homologation work, begun in this first phase of Task 5.1, will be completed in the second phase, the monitoring one between month 9 and month 30.

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

4 Assessment plans

4.1 RECONSTRUCT assessments

WP5 “Monitoring and assessment of impacts” will provide a set of assessments with the aim of monitoring short term and estimating medium- and long-term impacts of the project. It is important to consider all the 'products' of the project, from the new materials being studied, through the elements being created, to the two final demonstration buildings. By looking at the whole life cycle of the demonstrators, environmental as well as economic and social aspects will be evaluated.

Sustainability performance assessments are primarily conducted during the design stage, with limited monitoring of completed buildings. Evidence suggests that there may be a significant gap between estimated and actual building performance, sometimes up to 50%.ⁱ It is important to understand and learn from the various factors that contribute to this gap. In RECONSTRUCT we have the opportunity to assess all the stage of the lifecycle of the demos, from the material manufacturing to the end of life of the building. These results will be shown in the three “thematic” assessments:

- *D5.2 - LCA & LCC studies*, an analysis of impact of materials, products, and demo buildings throughout all the life cycle phases.
Related to *Task 5.2 (M30-M42) Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing* and to the work that will be done in *WP3 - Tracking, tracing, and digital twinning of construction elements* and *WP4 - Construction of circular demo buildings*.
- *D5.3 – Circularity assessment*, that assess the circularity and the symbiosis potential of the solutions.
Related to *Task 5.3 (M30-M42) Circularity Assessment & Symbiosis potential* and the work that will be done in *WP4 - Construction of circular demo buildings* and *WP6 - Social innovation and replication strategy* for the circularity part.
Related with the work that will be done in *WP1 AI-based sourcing and characterization of materials and waste* and *WP2 - Circular construction materials & components* for the Symbiosis potential part.
- *D5.4 – Social impact assessment*, that will focus on the social performance of the project.
Related to the *Task 5.4 (M30-M42) Social impact assessment*, and to most of the work that will be done in *WP3 - Tracking, tracing, and digital twinning of construction elements*, *WP6 - Social innovation and replication strategy* and *WP7 - Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation*.

One of the goals of the project is to measure the differences between the estimation during design stage and the as-built performance and understand the reason of these discrepancies. These analyses will help improve the simulation tools and method to better perform in the future. They will be carried out in the final “general” assessment:

- *D5.5 - Project impact assessment*, which will report the mid-to-long-term impact projections, the results of the development of a visual graphic BIM coding software and the unified heterogeneous dataset per material.
Related to the *Task 5.5 (M37-M48) Conducting simulations to estimate future impacts*, to the three “thematic” assessments listed above, and to the work that will be done in other WPs, especially *WP3 - Tracking, tracing, and digital twinning of construction elements* and *WP4 - Construction of circular demo buildings*.

As you can see from the list above, the task and assessment of *WP5 “Monitoring and assessment of impacts”* it is very connected to work that will be done in other WPs. There will be a great exchange of data that will come from various parts of the project: material and products manufacturing, building sites, BIM models, etc. The *WP5* assessments will need to get information from various data sources in order to run their simulations and calculations.

It will be important to structure the work plan and especially the data flow between WPs and also between the Tasks of *WP5*. This work was started in the first months of the *Task 5.1 Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring* and will continue in the next “phase” of the task. See chapter 9 – Conclusion of this document for more detail.

Figure 4.1 RECONSTRUCT Gantt Chart

The ability to compare data and results from different buildings is crucial to understanding how we can move towards a more sustainable future. To compare results produced using different methodologies, perhaps in geographically distant locations, it is important that the calculation method used reflects common guidelines.

There are several frameworks at EU level that help us to understand what kind of data should be analysed, from which sources and with which calculation methodology, if we want to arrive at codified and recognisable results.

Given the importance of meeting these EU standards, the first step was to analyse the structure and requirements of these frameworks.

4.2 EU frameworks

To guarantee the replicability of the RECONSTRUCT assessments and their validity outside the project competition, it is necessary to analyse the European references in the specific areas of each assessment.

Recognised European guidelines, frameworks and programmes are used as a guide to define the requirements of the documents produced within RECONSTRUCT, what data to analyse and how to process it, what definitions and units of measurement to use.

Adherence to European frameworks ensures that the work carried out within RECONSTRUCT can be disseminated throughout the EU and that the results can be compared with other projects and buildings analysed using the same methods.

The Level(s) frameworkⁱⁱ for assessing the sustainability of buildings is an initiative by the European Commission. Developed by the Directorate-General for Environment, it serves as a common and harmonised tool for evaluating and monitoring building sustainability within the European Union. Introduced in 2017, Level(s) is built upon 16 key indicators and aims to provide a shared methodology for measuring the sustainable performance of buildings. It is widespread among Europe and provides essential guidance on issues ranging from life-cycle studies to circularity assessment, covering the whole environmental impact of buildings.

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation, established in 2010 by British sailor Dame Ellen MacArthur, is a prominent non-profit organization dedicated to advancing the circular economy globally. In collaboration with Arup, a renowned design and engineering firm, the foundation developed the Circular Economy in the Built Environment Toolkit. This toolkit provides practical resources for integrating circular principles into construction projects. Additionally, the foundation partnered with Granta Design to create Circularity Indicators, a methodology focused on measuring and assessing the circularity of products and systems. These partnerships exemplify the foundation's commitment to practical solutions, strategic collaborations, and driving tangible progress towards a more sustainable and circular future.

The Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación's Re10Toolⁱⁱⁱ provides a methodology for analysing and verifying compliance with qualitative circularity criteria in new construction and refurbishment projects in terms of demolition and adaptability. It also defines a system for assessing the project, so that it can be considered whether the resulting building will meet minimum sustainability requirements in terms of demountability and adaptability.

These frameworks are based on the UNE-ISO 20887:2020 and her 2023 version, which focuses on sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works, with a specific emphasis on design for disassembly and adaptability. The standard establishes principles, requirements, and guidelines to encourage the design of buildings and civil engineering works that can be easily disassembled and adapted throughout their life cycle. The goal is to reduce environmental impacts, improve resource efficiency, and promote circularity in the construction sector. The standard provides a framework for industry practitioners to integrate sustainable practices from the early stages of the design and construction process.

4.2.1 LEVEL(s)

Level(s) is a framework created to measure the sustainability performance of buildings. It uses common indicators to calculate the required performance according to an established calculation model. This makes it possible to compare both new buildings and major renovation projects.

It aims to establish a common language of sustainability for buildings by defining core indicators for the sustainability of office and residential buildings.

The common framework provides a set of indicators and common metrics for measuring the sustainability performance of buildings along their life cycle, assessing the following aspects:

- environmental performance
- health and comfort,
- life cycle cost and value, and
- potential risks to future performance.

Level(s) is based on 6 macro-objectives, which describe the strategic priorities that the construction sector must address to contribute to the EU's sustainable development: energy, material use and waste, water, indoor air quality and the long-term value of goods.

For each of these strategic priorities, it is important that the contribution and performance of individual building projects can be measured. Indicators have therefore been developed that enable the measurement of performance under each macro-objective.

The Level(s) common framework consists of 16 core indicators. Each indicator has been selected to measure the performance and contribution of a building towards a specific macro-objective. An overview of the indicators and their units of measurement is provided in the table below.

For each strategic priority, it is essential to measure the performance and impact of individual construction projects. To achieve this, specific indicators have been developed to facilitate the assessment of project performance against overarching objectives.

The Level(s) universal framework comprises 16 basic indicators, carefully selected to measure the effectiveness of a building and its contribution to a specific macro-objective. A comprehensive table below provides an overview of these indicators along with their respective units of measurement.

For the purpose of the project, the main focus will be on the indicators of the macro-objective 1 – Greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions along building's life cycle, 2 – Resource efficient and circular material life cycles, and 6 – Optimised life cycle cost and value.

Each assessment will focus of some specific indicators, LCC will comply with the indicators in Objective 6, the Circular Assessment will focus mainly on the indicators in macro-objective 2. It will be frequent that some Level(s) indicators will be considered in more than one assessment, like the 2.1 Bill of quantities, materials, and lifespans.

It is clear that managing the source of the data needed to calculate these indicators is crucial to have the same value for different assessments.

The D5.5 Project Impact Assessment will provide a Level(s) report at the end of the project, using the info already elaborated in the previous assessment, respecting the EU framework.

Macro-objective	Indicator	Unit of measurement
1: Greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions along a building's life cycle	1.1 Use stage energy performance	kilowatt hours per square metre per year (kWh/m ² /yr)
	1.2 Life cycle Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ equivalents per square metre per year (kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /yr)
2. Resource efficient and circular material life cycles	2.1 Bill of quantities, materials and lifespans	Unit quantities, mass and years
	2.2 Construction & demolition waste and materials	kg of waste and materials per m ² total useful floor area
	2.3 Design for adaptability and renovation	Adaptability score
	2.4 Design for deconstruction, reuse and recycling	Deconstruction score
3. Efficient use of water resources	3.1 Use stage water consumption	m ³ /yr of water per occupant
4. Healthy and comfortable spaces	4.1 Indoor air quality	Parameters for ventilation, CO ₂ and humidity Target list of pollutants: TVOC, formaldehyde, CMR VOC, LCI ratio, mould, benzene, particulates, radon
	4.2 Time outside of thermal comfort range	% of the time out of range during the heating and cooling seasons
	4.3 Lighting and visual comfort	Level 1 checklist
	4.4 Acoustics and protection against noise	Level 1 checklist
5. Adaptation and resilience to climate change	5.1 Protection of occupier health and thermal comfort	Projected % time out of range in the years 2030 and 2050 (see also indicator 4.2)
	5.2 Increased risk of extreme weather events	Level 1 checklist (under development)
	5.3 Increased risk of flood events	Level 1 checklist (under development)
6. Optimised life cycle cost and value	6.1 Life cycle costs	Euros per square metre per year (€/m ² /yr)
	6.2 Value creation and risk exposure	Level 1 checklist

Figure 4.2 Level(s)' Indicators

As the name suggests, the framework is divided into three levels, each relating to a different phase of a building project and with different objectives.

- Level 1. The conceptual design for the building project – the simplest level as it entails early-stage qualitative assessments.
- Level 2. The detailed design and construction performance of the building – an intermediate level as it entails a quantitative assessment.
- Level 3. The as-built and in-use performance of how the building performs after completion and handover to the client – the most advanced level as it entails the monitoring and surveying.

Progression through the levels also means an increase in the accuracy and reliability of the reporting. The higher the level, the closer the reported results will be to providing you with data that reflects the performance of the building as built and in use.

Once the impacts of the building have been measured at different stages of the project, a fundamental part of the Level(s) framework is the ability to compare results between buildings with similar functions.

To ensure a meaningful comparison, it is essential that the indicators provide guidance on how they should be evaluated.

How comparability is supported by using Level(s):

- Use of the common units of measurement
- Completion of the Level(s) building description
- Use of the cited reference standards and methods
- The required reporting on key parameters, assumptions, and data quality, in order to ensure transparency
- The rules stipulated that are specific to Level(s) and which: fix key parameters, provide default data, and define calculation assumptions.

The Level(s) common framework takes a whole life cycle approach to the sustainability of buildings. To fully support this approach, the core indicators of macro-objectives 1, 2 and 3 are complemented by a holistic assessment of a building's environmental impact - a full Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of a building. By making a LCA, the environmental impacts associated with a building can be quantified and the most significant areas – commonly referred to as "hot spots" – can be identified and used as the starting point for improving performance.

4.2.2 Ellen MacArthur

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation, established in 2010 by British sailor Dame Ellen MacArthur, is a globally renowned non-profit organization dedicated to accelerating the transition to a circular economy. The foundation's mission is to inspire and drive the adoption of circular economic principles across industries and sectors worldwide.

It has gained widespread recognition across Europe and from the European Community for its pioneering advocacy, strategic partnerships with major entities, educational initiatives,

and development of practical tools like the Circularity Indicators project, in partnership with Granta Design, and the the Circular Economy in the Built Environment Toolkit, in partnership with Arup.

The Circular Indicators project was developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation in partnership with Granta Design. The project was co-funded by the European Union's LIFE financial instrument. The aim is to provide indicators for assessing the circularity of products and companies.

It offers tools and indicators to guide companies towards greater circularity, helping them to make informed decisions on the trade-offs between circularity and economic, environmental, and social objectives related to product design and material sourcing.

The project has focused on quantifying the restoration of material flows and the development of a Material Circularity Indicator (MCI). Other considerations (e.g. toxicity, scarcity, and energy) are included as complementary indicators.

The indicators have been developed on a product and company level. The Circularity Indicators methodology also contains a section giving guidance to help estimate the profitability of circular economy business initiatives.

Figure 4.3 Material flows considered to arrive at the Material Circularity Indicator of a product. ^{iv}

It considers inputs from several sources:

- Input in the production process: How much input is coming from virgin and recycled materials and reused components?

- Utility during use phase: How long and intensely is the product used compared to an industry average product of similar type? This considers increased durability of products, but also repair/maintenance and shared consumption business models.
- Destination after use: How much material goes into landfill (or energy recovery), how much is collected for recycling, which components are collected for reuse?
- Efficiency of recycling: How efficient are the recycling processes used to produce recycled input and to recycle material after use?
- A detailed bill of materials for the product is needed to compute the MCI, listing the above data for all its components and materials.

Considering these inputs plus some complementary risks and impact indicators, the MCI calculations gives is a value between 0 and 1 to a product or to a company, with higher values indicate higher circularity.

4.2.3 RE10 tool

The RE10 Tool developed by the Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación (IVE) is a tool that analyses and verifies compliance with sustainability criteria in new construction and building renovation projects, with a focus on disassembly and adaptability.

The main goal of RE10 is to assess how well a building project aligns with sustainability criteria, particularly in terms of the ability to disassemble and adapt building elements. It is based on the ISO 20887:2020 standard, which establishes principles for evaluating the disassembly and adaptability of products.

The analysis considers various criteria, including:

- Disassembly: It evaluates how easily building elements can be disassembled without damage.
- Adaptability: It examines the building's capacity to adapt to new uses or needs over time.

The RE10 Tool provides a methodology for assessing sustainability levels in terms of disassembly and adaptability. It can be used for both new construction and renovation projects, making it a valuable resource for architects, engineers, and building professionals to evaluate and enhance the sustainability of building projects and verifying if the project could apply to the EU Next Generation funding.

HERRAMIENTA DE ANÁLISIS DEL DESMONTAJE Y LA ADAPTABILIDAD EN PROYECTOS DE EDIFICACIÓN

R. RESULTADOS			
RESUMEN DE CRITERIOS EVALUADOS			
C1. VERSATILIDAD		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C2. CONVERTIBILIDAD		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C3. CAPACIDAD DE AMPLIACIÓN		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C4. FACILIDAD DE ACCESO A COMPONENTES Y SERVICIOS		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C5. INDEPENDENCIA Y CONEXIONES REVERSIBLES		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C6. EVITAR TRATAMIENTOS Y ACABADOS INNECESARIOS		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C7. APOYO A LA ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C8. EFICIENCIA EN EL PROCESO CONSTRUCTIVO		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C9. SEGURIDAD DEL DESMONTAJE		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
C10. DURABILIDAD		IR A LA FICHA	NO CUMPLE
TOTAL DE CRITERIOS EVALUADOS	10	TOTAL DE CRITERIOS CUMPLIDOS	0
PORCENTAJE DE CRITERIOS CUMPLIDOS (%)	0%	NIVEL DE CLASIFICACIÓN OBTENIDO	FALTA PUNTUACIÓN

Figure 4.4 Table of results and evaluation criteria of R10 Tool. ^v

Co-funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

4.2.4 S-LCA guidelines by UNEP

The Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of Products, developed by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), provide a roadmap and a body of knowledge for stakeholders engaged in assessing the social and socio-economic impacts of product life cycles. These guidelines cover the entire life cycle of products, from the extraction of natural resources to final disposal.

The S-LCA aims to assess and report on the impacts and benefits related to social aspects throughout a product’s life cycle. It goes beyond environmental considerations to include social dimensions. The guidelines offer a robust technical framework for conducting S-LCA. They provide guidance on data collection, impact assessment, and reporting. Stakeholders can use this methodology to evaluate social responsibility when assessing goods and services. The Social assessment considers various aspects, such as labour conditions, human rights, health and safety, community well-being, and socio-economic factors. It helps identify potential hotspots and areas for improvement.

The S-LCA can complement environmental life cycle assessments (LCA) and economic assessments. Integrating social aspects into decision-making processes enhances overall sustainability.

These guidelines serve as a valuable resource for practitioners, policymakers, and organizations striving for more socially responsible and sustainable product development and consumption.

Figure 4.5 Assessment system from categories to unit of measurement. ^{vi}

5 LCA & LCC

5.1 Description

The growing awareness regarding the importance of environmental protection, cost efficiency and the possible impacts associated with products, manufactured, or consumed, have risen the interest in method development to better comprehend and manage those impacts. Two of the developed techniques in this field are the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) representing two of the sustainability pillars (Environmental and Economic respectively).

Figure 5.1 Three pillars of sustainability.

The LCA addresses the environmental aspects and potential environmental impacts (for example, the use of resources and the consequential emissions associated) along the life cycle of the material, product or building from the acquisition of raw materials, through the production of the materials, products or components, its use, final waste treatment, recycling, until its final disposal (from cradle to grave).

The LCC addresses the economic behaviour expressed in economic terms throughout the life cycle. Unlike traditional cost analysis, which typically focuses on upfront and initial costs, LCC considers costs over the entire life span of the object of study (material, product, or building), taking into consideration the negative costs associated to energy export and reuse and recycling of product or building parts, both during its life cycle and at the end of its service life.

Figure 5.2 The product life cycle stages. Extracted from a PRé Sustainability B.V. article

The LCA and LCC consists of four phases of study:

1. Objective definition and scope.
2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis.
3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) evaluation.
4. Interpretation.

Figure 5.3 Four steps of life cycle assessment. Extracted from a PRé Sustainability B.V. article.

The objective and scope of the LCA/LCC, including the limits of the system and level of detail, depend on the topic and the study's intended use. In RECONSTRUCT, the intended use is clear and defined by the project's KPI's:

- At a material level:
 - Virgin material content: 0%.
 - Recyclability: 100%.
 - GHG embodied: 80% less than ordinary Portland cement.
- At a product level:
 - Virgin material content: 20%.
 - Durability: 2 times more than legacy components.
 - Performance: Equal or better than traditional components.
- At a building level:
 - Building GHG embodied: 80% less than traditional building.
 - Construction waste: 90% less than traditional building.
 - Recycled content: 90%.
 - Non-renewable content: 5%.
 - Closed-loop Construction Demolition Waste (CDW) recycling: 30-50% more than traditional building.

With the before mentioned KPI's, the scope should include the whole life cycle (cradle to grave) and in some cases even further beyond the scope (cradle to cradle). An LCA should be carried out at all levels (material, product and building) so a high level of detail will be necessary.

The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is the second phase of an LCA and LCC. Is an inventory of inputs and outputs in relation to the scope and objectives under study. In this plan, a pre-assessment of the needed inputs for our goal outcomes have been studied and listed in this document (section 5.2).

The evaluation of the life cycle's impacts or costs (LCIA) is the third phase. The main objective of this phase is to provide additional information to assist the evaluation of the life cycle inventory to better understand its environmental importance and cost effectiveness.

Lastly, an interpretation of the results is needed to arrive to conclusions, propose recommendations and improve the decision-making process accordingly to the objectives and scope defined. This information will be used to define optimization scenarios and strategies to achieve the objectives set by RECONSTRUCT.

5.1.1 State of the art

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) provides standards (e.g., EN 14040^{vii}, EN 14044^{viii}, EN 15804^{ix}, EN 15978^x and EN 16627^{xi}) that outline the principles and framework for conducting life cycle analysis for environmental and cost performance of products and buildings.

LCA is a valuable methodology for businesses, policymakers, and consumers to make more informed decisions regarding the environmental implications of products and processes. It is currently use (in different degrees of application) for eco-design, product labelling, environmental performance communication, and policy development. LCA is also closely related to other sustainability assessment tools and methodologies, such as carbon footprinting, decarbonization and environmental product declarations (EPDs).

LCC is commonly used in various industries, including construction, product manufacturing and public institutions (e.g., green public procurement). It is particularly valuable for assessing the economic viability of different alternatives, guiding investment decisions, and optimizing resources over the entire life span of a project or product.

Both LCA and LCC continue to evolve as tools for evaluating the environmental and economic impacts of products and systems. The integration of these approaches can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the overall sustainability of a product or project.

According to RAMBOLL's "Review of existing national legislative measures^{xii}", the most advanced countries in Europe regarding Whole Life Carbon (WLC) models are Denmark, Finland, France, the Netherlands, and Sweden. All these countries have reporting requirements on embodied carbon emissions in place for new buildings, accompanied by limit values. They show that regulation of buildings' environmental footprint beyond operational energy is possible and useful for decision-making and that can be implemented in a national scale. All five country frameworks include methodologies of life-cycle assessments of buildings based on international standards (mentioned in this document) which are also the main reference for the European framework Level(s) (section 4.2.1).

These country specific frameworks will be taken into consideration when defining policy recommendations and fulfilling upcoming requirements like the revision of the Energy Performance Building Directive (EPBD)^{xiii}: "The life-cycle Global Warming Potential (GWP) of new buildings will have to be calculated as of 2030 in accordance with the Level(s) framework, thus informing on the whole-life cycle emissions of new construction. Whole-life cycle emissions are particularly relevant for large buildings, which is why the obligation to calculate them already applies to large buildings (with a useful floor area larger than 2000 square meters) as of 2027."

5.1.2 Strengths and weaknesses

Strengths

- Comprehensive analysis: when performing an LCA/LCC a holistic view of the environmental and cost impacts is provided through its entire life cycle, helping identify potential areas for improvement.
- Systematic analysis: LCA and LCC follow a systematic approach guided by international standards (EN 15804 for environmental analysis for construction materials and products, EN 15978 for environmental performance for buildings

and EN 16627 for economic performance of buildings), ensuring consistency and objectiveness across different assessments.

- Comparative analysis: LCA and LCC facilitates the comparison of alternative scenarios by identifying the most appropriate solution.
- Informed decision-making: LCA and LCC result can inform decision-makers about environmental and cost performance of alternatives, aiding in sustainable product development, building design and policy recommendations.
- Integration with other metrics: An LCI is needed for both frameworks, LCA and LCC, but it can also be used for other metrics, such as material passport and circularity assessment, providing a more useful sustainability assessment.
- Combination of LCA and LCC: The combination of both frameworks and assessments can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sustainability of a material, product, or building, considering both environmental and economic aspects.

Weaknesses

- Data quality and availability: Obtaining accurate and comprehensive data for all stages of the life cycle can be challenging. Data gaps or inaccuracies can impact the reliability of LCA and LCC results.
- Simplifications and assumptions: models often involve simplifications and assumptions due to lack of information or complexity of real-world systems. These scenarios can introduce inaccuracies and uncertainties into the assessment.
- Limited standardization for LCC: Unlike LCA, which has more standardized methods and tools, LCC methodologies may vary, leading to challenging comparisons between different studies.
- Complexity and subjectivity: LCA and LCC can be complex and subjective, especially when analysing future impacts or costs.

5.2 Partner's methodology

For the assessments of LCA and LCC, TCQi GMA by ITeC is to be used, a software that allows you to elaborate studies for a project based on environmental indicators and cost analysis. Some capabilities to be used in this project include:

- Environmental life cycle assessment and life cycle costing.
- Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) management.
- Compatibility with BIM and other BC3 format software.
- Disassembly potential

Since the RECONSTRUCT project is structured taking into account a staggered development of the elements to be analysed in the demonstrations, first materials (alkali activated cement or AAC, alkali activated cement-based concrete or AACC and textile reinforced recycled concrete or TRRC), then construction elements (precast pavement blocks and façade panels, sandwich floor panels and in-situ casting for foundations and pillars) and finally the construction of the demonstrative (Brussels and Barcelona), the LCA

and LCC is divided into these 3 levels of analysis: material, product and building. The main objective for this approach is guarantee compatibility with the digitalization necessary for tasks in WP3 (Tracking, tracing, and digital twinning of construction elements) that requires traceability from start to finish. This is why both the LCA and LCC will be performed following these steps:

Step 1: LCA of materials and database digitalization

An LCA is performed for the different types of materials including their alternatives. For the analysis, information from the manufacturer and/or research centre will be needed (listed in inputs section below). To avoid data quality and availability issues, when no empirical data or specific datasets are available, a selection of generic datasets will be used from recognised databases in the sector like Ecoinvent or ITeC's database, BEDEC.

The final LCA results, together with the expected retail price, will be digitalised in a small database to be used by WP3 and for smooth optimization of the final solutions.

Step 2: LCA and LCC of products and data incorporation into the BIM object

Using the previous information from Step 1 and additional material information for construction elements manufacturing, an LCA and LCC will be carried out per construction element. This construction element should be equivalent to the BIM object created for BIM model development. To avoid data quality and availability issues, when no empirical data or specific datasets are available, a selection of generic datasets will be used from ITeC's database, BEDEC.

Step 3: LCA and LCC of demonstration buildings

Whole building analysis with TCQi GMA for LCA and LCC for life stages: product manufacturing, construction, use and end-of-life. During this step, two LCA and LCC models per demonstrator will be created, a baseline and the RECONSTRUCT solution. Both models per demonstrator will be used to check the KPIs compliance.

Step 4: LCA and LCC of optimization scenarios

Alternative scenarios analysis for 6D-BIM tool optimization.

5.2.1 Input required

The list of inputs required to perform the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) at a material, product and building level is shown below:

- Material level:
 - Raw material quantities (quantitative, 'kg' or 'm³'):
The main objective is to identify the nature of the raw material needed for the product and to assign the environmental impact to each ingredient. It will be also needed the raw materials needed for the packaging of the final product.
 - Distance from/to providers (quantitative, 'km'):

The main objective is to assign each raw material its supply impact. It may happen that the same raw material is supplied by more than one supplier, in this case, we would need the amount of raw material that each supplier has supplied and how far away they are.

- Manufacturing waste (quantitative, 'kg'):
Waste produced by product-related processes. As a minimum, the waste should be proportional part of the packaging materials and extra raw materials added. It will be also needed the distance and type of transport (usually truck) to the waste management for each type of waste (wood, plastic, hazardous, etc...).
- Energy and water consumptions (quantitative, 'kWh' or 'MJ' and 'm³'):
The main objective is to collect the energy and water needed to manufacture the materials. Ideally, we would need the kWh/MJ of each energy resource per material (electricity, gas, etc...).
- Background database data for raw materials not included in RECONSTRUCT (qualitative):
When background information (not produced by the project) is needed, ITeC's generic database (BEDEC) and Ecoinvent will be used as a reference.
- Recycled or renewable content (quantitative, 'kg'):
Identify quantities of raw material with circular origins (recycled, reused, renewable). If mass not available, a percentage of the total weight will suffice.
- **Product level:**
 - Bill of Materials (BoM) of the final product (qualitative):
The main objective is to account for all primary quantities (quantities entering the manufacturing processes) needed for the product under study. If these primary quantities are not available, documents such as composition and yield data will suffice.
 - Manufacturing waste (quantitative, 'kg'):
Waste produced by product-related processes. As a minimum, the waste should be proportional part of the packaging materials and extra raw materials added. It will be also needed the distance and type of transport (usually truck) to the waste management for each type of waste (wood, plastic, hazardous, etc...).
 - Energy and water consumptions (quantitative, 'kWh' or 'MJ' and 'm³'):
The main objective is to collect the energy and water needed to manufacture the final product. Ideally, we would need the kWh/MJ of each energy resource per product (electricity, gas, etc...).
 - Background database data for materials not included in RECONSTRUCT (qualitative):
When background information (not produced by the project) is needed, ITeC's generic database (BEDEC) and Ecoinvent will be used as a reference.
 - Environmental and cost indicators for materials (quantitative, multiple units):
Cost and environmental impacts following EN 15804 for all materials needed for the product manufacturing. These indicators will include all the parameters requested by modern EPDs.
 - Waste classification (EWC) (quantitative, 'kg'):

Waste categorization using the European Waste Code (EWC) for waste management and symbiosis integration. Final product should be also categorized with an EWC for its accounting in construction and end-of-life processes.

- Potential disassembly (quantitative, '%'):
The main objective is to account for its disassembly being the separation of its constituent materials and/or as product as a whole.
- Recycled or renewable content (quantitative, '%'):
Identify quantities of raw material with circular origins (recycled, reused, renewable). If raw materials already have this information, the final values of the product will be calculated.
- Expected maintenance activities (qualitative):
The main objective is to account for all expected maintenance activities during the use stage of the product and demonstrator.
- Product lifespan (quantitative, 'years'):
Expected lifespan of the product for comparison between different solutions and good allocation of use stage activities.
- BIM object (qualitative):
Product digitalized in BIM for integration in full scale building an dynamic BIM data analysis.
- **Building level:**
 - Bill of Quantities (BoQ) or Building's Material Passport (qualitative):
The main objective is to account for all material quantities (quantities entering the construction processes) needed for the demonstrator under study. These primary quantities will be categorized for Building Material Passport development.
 - Construction waste (quantitative, 'kg'):
Waste produced by product-installation processes. As a minimum, the waste should be proportional part of the packaging materials and extra auxiliary materials added. It will be also needed the distance and type of transport (usually truck) to the waste management for each type of waste (wood, plastic, hazardous, etc...).
 - Energy and water consumptions during construction stage (quantitative, 'kWh' or 'MJ' and 'm³'):
The main objective is to collect the energy and water needed to build the demonstrator. Ideally, we would need the kWh/MJ of each energy resource (electricity, gas, etc...).
 - Background database data for construction processes not included in RECONSTRUCT (qualitative):
When background information (not produced by the project) is needed, ITeC's generic database (BEDEC) will be used as a reference.
 - Environmental and cost indicators for products (quantitative, multiple units):
Cost and environmental impacts following EN 15804 for all materials needed for the product manufacturing. These indicators will include all the parameters requested by modern EPDs.
 - Construction cost (quantitative, '€'):

- Cost of the construction process of the demonstrator buildings. These costs will need to include labour, machinery, auxiliary materials and products.
- Costs of reusing each material of interest (quantitative, '€'):
Price of the recycled material to be reused in new buildings. Could include final market price and/or recycling costs for each of the treatments it must undergo to fit a new purpose, as well as the costs of transport of such materials.
 - Demolition waste (quantitative, 'kg'):
Waste produced by demolition or disassembly processes. As a minimum, the waste should be same quantity as the total weight of the demonstrator. It will be also needed the distance and type of transport (usually truck) to the waste management for each type of waste (wood, plastic, hazardous, etc...).
 - Energy and water consumptions during end-of-life stage (quantitative, 'kWh' or 'MJ' and 'm³'):
The main objective is to collect the energy and water needed to demolish or disassemble the demonstrator. Ideally, we would need the kWh/MJ of each energy resource (electricity, gas, etc...).
 - Demolition/Disassembly cost (quantitative, '€'):
Cost of the demolition or disassembly process of the demonstrator buildings. These costs will need to include labour, machinery, and auxiliary materials.
 - Waste recycling or disposal cost and emissions (quantitative, 'kg'):
Cost and environmental impacts following EN 15804 for end-of-life waste processing. These indicators will include all the parameters requested by modern EPDs.
 - BIM model (qualitative):
A BIM model will be needed to guarantee a dynamic representation of the LCA and LCC data.

5.2.2 Output obtained

The list of outputs obtained after performing the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) at a material, product and building level is shown below:

- Material level:
 - Environmental and cost indicators per material (quantitative, multiple units):
Cost and environmental impacts following EN 15804 for all materials needed for the product manufacturing. These indicators will include all the parameters requested by modern EPDs.
- Product level:
 - Environmental and cost indicators per product (quantitative, multiple units):
Cost and environmental impacts following EN 15804 for all products needed for the demonstrator construction. These indicators will include all the parameters requested by modern EPDs.
 - Information for Material passport development of the final product (qualitative):
Reporting of Material passport of products for Building Material Passport development.
 - BIM object with connected environmental and cost information (qualitative):

Product digitalization with environmental and cost information for digital twin utilization.

- Building level:
 - Environmental and cost indicators for the building (quantitative, multiple units):
Final cost and environmental impacts following EN 15978 for the whole demonstrator building.
 - Level(s) structured report (qualitative):
Reporting of final cost and environmental impacts following Level(s) framework (Macro Objectives 1, 2 and 6).
 - BIM model with dynamic environmental and cost information (qualitative):
Demonstrator digital twin with environmental and cost information dynamically adjusted through the modelling tools.

6 Circularity Assessment

6.1 Description

The circularity assessment of RECONSTRUCT will be Deliverable D5.3, the result of Task 5.3. It will consist of two 'cores', a general part on measuring the circularity of the construction process, and a specific part on the potential for reuse of CDW materials in other production processes, called the symbiosis potential.

The partner leader of the first part, the general part on circularity in Subtask 5.3.1, will be SOO. The leader of Subtask 5.3.2 concerning the symbiosis potential is SYM.

The D5.3 - Circularity Assessment will give an overview of all values of circularity and therefore both "souls" of the deliverable are planned in this chapter.

Circularity Assessment

The assessment of circularity is necessary because it highlights the limitations of the planet, such as the predicted scarcity of virgin resources and the large accumulation and need to manage the waste generated in the different sectors of activity, as well as the modification of the environment resulting from this resource extraction and waste disposal.

The concept of circularity means closing the cycle of the 3 resource streams as much as possible: materials-waste, energy, and water, as shown in figure 6.1. Within the construction sector, it means minimizing the extraction of virgin materials, including fossil fuels, and avoiding the generation of waste either in the construction and subsequent use stage or in the final demolition of the building, as shown in figure 6.2.

This is achieved using renewable materials/resources, the continuous reuse or recycling of these materials and resources (waste, water, energy) within the production chain of a building, the design of construction solutions that enable final disassembly and separation into independent materials for recycling or reuse, extending the useful life of the product whenever possible, and the correct management of waste. This concept is opposed to the current linear 'take-make-waste' economy.

According to Circle Economy, the world was only 8.6% circular in 2021^{xiv}. This is just one of the indicators that have been proposed to measure the progress of the circular economy.

Figure 6.1 Open and Closed loop (circular) of resources. Source: Societat Orgànica

Figure 6.2 Stages of lifecycle of a building to close the loop (green and blue stages). Source: Societat Orgànica

The circular assessment developed in this case, will focus on the material and waste stream, the water resource will be discarded from this analysis and the energy flow will be included in the LCA assessment as they are not the object of the experiments sought in this project. This is so, in part, because in the case of the Spanish demo, neither electricity nor water will be provided. In the case of the Belgian demo, the possible measurement of the energy consumed will be evaluated and included in the LCA (fossil energy outputs versus renewable energy).

There are several ways to assess environmentally a building, and besides Circular Assessment, the LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) and the LCC (Life Cycle Costing) are two of them there are directly related through various indicators.

However, there are currently no harmonized definitions of what a circularity analysis is meaning a unique methodology, global indicator, or tool since it must cover different stages of life cycle and future scenarios difficult to define.

The need for a more circular economy has been translated into European directives that are replicated in national regulations. Change is difficult within the construction sector. There are concerns within the European Commission (EC), international regulations and other standards regarding the Circular Economy and CDW. In this sense, the EC presented an ambitious Circular Economy Package, this comprises updated legislative suggestions on waste management, aiming to encourage Europe's shift towards a circular economy. The goal is to enhance global competitiveness, promote sustainable economic expansion, and create employment opportunities^{xv}.

The difficulties are partially since there is currently no harmonised and holistic European framework on circularity between EU countries or even in public administration^{xvi} like certificates schemes of circularity, different approaches to the assessment of circularity, public regulation, lack of long-term statistic's, etc.

What do exist are frameworks from recognized institutions or projects such as the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Circle Economy or BUS Go-Circular, or tools, developed to identify part of this analysis at different levels of project development, such as the Circular Economy in the Built Environment developed by Arup and Ellen MacArthur Foundation for strategic decisions in the early stages of the project, RE10 Tool for the analysis of disassembly and adaptability in the retrofitting of residential buildings developed by Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación (IVE), the COAC questionnaires adapting the Do No Harm to the Environment (DNHS) principle or the Material Circular Indicator developed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Based on these references and others identified in the State of Art of the project, together with the experience of the consortium partners and external stakeholders, a list of indicators has been defined to define the circularity concept in this project and which is intended to be a replicable methodology for the building sector. This evaluation is explained in the section 6.2 of this document.

Symbiosis Potential

The symbiosis potential consists in the evaluation of multiple valorisations routes for the materials that are to be reused within the pilots. Since both pilots in Spain and Brussels have been designed for being deconstructed, the assessment of this potential is relevant for finding valorisation routes for those materials whose direct reutilisation in other sites is not feasible. The information used for estimating the potential it is directly connected with the indicators studied in the circularity assessment such as the state of the material after use, their price, location of possible markets, intermediate technologies to make the fit for a new purpose –where necessary-, among others. These pieces of information are to be populated into Synerplatform, where lists of potential *takers* and companies who can provide intermediate process for transforming it into a valuable recycled material will be identified.

6.1.1 State of the art

An EU-funded project called SCALER^{xvii} has delved into the state of the art of symbiosis potential tools and methods. These are mainly comprised of databases and platforms that in many cases are context specific or show generic synergies between specific by-products. According to their findings, after analysing over 20 of such tools they concluded that their accessibility and applicability are uncertain for those in charge of carrying out industrial symbiosis projects. Moreover, it can be seen that some of the tools were developed withing

European-funded schemes like H2020 or Life projects and have not been exploited beyond the timeframe of the project. Consequently, they are at an early stage and lack of support and functional links to make use of them.

6.1.2 Strengths and weaknesses

Strengths of circularity assessment and symbiosis potential:

- Provision of a holistic perspective: considering the entire life cycle of products or processes and lifespan of the buildings. This enables a comprehensive understanding of its real environmental impacts.
- Use of sustainability metrics: employ well-defined sustainability metrics, providing a standardised way to measure and compare environmental performance of the buildings, giving a common language, comprehensive and validated indicators to enable and facilitate decision making of the different actors involved.
- Create databases: Related to the use of a common assessment system, knowing the flow of material, energy, and waste at a high level of detail allows for focused strategies and decision making based on measurable indicators. Transforming data into valuable indicators.
- Promotion of resource efficiency contributes to making decisions in order to minimise waste, maintain, extend the lifespan and reuse of the materials and conserve the resources by avoiding the extraction of raw materials.
- Innovation stimulation: pushing companies and industries to find creative solutions and technology for reducing environmental footprints. For example, new strategies of constructive solutions connections allowing its deconstruction for reuse, new design methods such as BIM allowing the behaviour prediction and coordinating faculties of AEC projects or recycling waste materials between industries to reduce waste.
- Mitigation of risks: diversifying resource streams and reducing dependence on finite resources, which oftentimes incur in price volatility.
- Promote new business models: Consider other business models that are based on the interaction between products and services or that value opportunities that participate in circularity at some stage of the life cycle of a building-product. Create materials reuse markets or networks, value of the deconstruction auditors, repair and maintenance service inside the product supply, extended responsibility producer models, symbiosis between surrounding industries or facilities are some of possible alternatives.
- Advance knowledge: Develop research, encourage innovation networks, create recognised circularity frameworks (methodologies, tools) and disseminate findings to provide structured knowledge and upskilling the workforce.
- Possibility to collaborate between different actors in the value chain: To ensure the proper performance throughout all phases of a building's life cycle (waste management, proper disassembly, pre-designed selection of materials and systems, maintenance management, etc.) and to carry out the planned circularity enhancement measures, it is necessary to coordinate and collaborate between the different agents involved along the value chain and in the different phases of the building's life cycle.

It also generates the possibility of increasing networking and discovering opportunities to design collaborative solutions.

- Collaborate to create joint value: Work together throughout the supply chain, internally within organisations and with the public sector to increase transparency and create joint value.
- Reduction of the environmental footprint: When a plan is made from the beginning considering the whole life cycle of the building or product, coordinating all stages and actors, a reduction of the environmental impact can be achieved: extending the life span, avoiding waste and recycling resources.
- Cost reduction: Related to carbon footprint reduction and resource efficiency, as the optimisation of the systems and reuse of materials, products and equipment, cost reductions can be achieved in different Life Cycle stages.
- Material Product and Building Passports: Possibility to develop materials passport identifying each product or actor needs.

Weaknesses of circularity assessment and symbiosis potential:

- Availability of data: reliable data is crucial for accurate assessments, but obtaining comprehensive and standardised data on material flows and environmental impacts can be difficult. Related to the use of a common assessment system, having data to measure circularity at a high level of detail remains a challenge especially in the flow of raw materials and energy in production chains or in building operation, with more information on waste monitoring and recovery rates, although not always in a transparent or harmonised way.
- Trade-offs: it may involve trade-offs, such as increased energy use during recycling or the need for more extensive transportation networks. Assessments need to consider these trade-offs.
- Scenarios definition: there are currently European standards in force on life cycle analysis at both product and building level that define the characteristics and methodologies for the calculation of LCA (including some circularity indicators). In some stages of the life cycle, it is necessary to assume scenarios for its calculation, such as the maintenance, repair, refurbishment, or end-of-life stage. Although the regulations are more specific at the product level than at the building level, there are still scenarios with poor or open definition that generate the difficult harmonisation of these, the difficulty to find statistical data from recognised sources and/or real measurements; giving rise to circular indicators that may incur in subjective scenarios and creating less universal assessments.
- Need for expertise: The use of digital and mechanical technologies requires specialised knowledge by the workers. The use of some indicators and circular concepts in the decision making for the whole life cycle need for higher qualified workforce and up-skills strategies.
- Lack of harmonisation in knowledge & Up-skilling: Although there are projects that propose holistic training frameworks on circularity such as BUS-Go Circular and the efforts of several autonomous administrations of European regions and other

organisations such as Ellen MacArthur or Level(s) in creating methods to assess circularity and/or adaptability, it is still necessary to translate and transfer this information into curricular plans, professional guides and tools harmonised between the different entities and European countries and the promotion of the Up-skilling of the workforce. For this, obviously, data collection and systemic circular solutions are needed first.

- Collaboration though the value chain: This point is both a strength and a weakness. Working together, collaboration between businesses and different profiles (white collar, blue collar, industry) is necessary to achieve circularity throughout the whole life cycle and not in independent stages where the loss of understanding leads to the incorrect circular performance of the building or to the loss of symbiosis between industries that could share resources. The weakness lies in the difficulty of collaboration and communication between all the agents involved in the value chain of the different phases and/or in the transfer of the appropriate information in a shared system, such as BIM platforms. The strength lies in making this opportunity for collaboration possible and detecting the most efficient joint processes.
- Lack of regulations and standards: Despite having normative standards and reports on LCA, there are still few regulations on the methodology and practices in circularity assessments. On the other hand, there are guidelines, some voluntary tools and Action Plans.
- High initial material costs: Often, the choice of materials or systems that close the loop ("circular"), renewable energy production systems or the design for deconstruction (dry), may result in higher initial prices or not immediate amortisation, especially if there has not been good planning from the beginning and collaboration between all the agents involved. Some investments must be evaluated in the long term.
- Lack of monitoring: To control performance, maintenance, quality monitoring, disassemblability, recyclability and durability, rigorous monitoring and evaluations are required at all stages of the life cycle, especially at the use and end-of-life stage. Thus, it is possible to obtain real and reliable data on the stages of use of the building (maintenance, rehabilitation, replacement, use) and the end-of-life cycle (disassembly, waste, treatment).
- Lack of awareness or interest: in reuse, choice of materials, sustainability, etc.

6.2 Methodology for the assessment

Circularity Assessment

For the assessment of circularity, we do not propose a single indicator that makes it possible to evaluate the greater or lesser circularity of a building. We agree that it would be an impossible task to give exclusive importance to a single aspect or indicator in this case, as in LCA we don't only measure kgCO₂ eq. without paying attention to the rest of impact indicators.

Based on the different existing frameworks and tools analysed and on the own experience of partners of the consortium in the environmental consultancy of architectural projects, we propose instead a series of indicators that will be able to demonstrate circularity in wider spectrum and along the stages of the life cycle. Adaptability will be included as an indicator of circularity as well. Once we have obtained all the indicators that we consider that represents the circularity of a building considering various circular strategies, we will intend to group the indicators by categories and suggest a weighting between them that gives different weight to each one. Ultimately, three summary indicators will be proposed to make the effort to combine the circular potential in each stage of life cycle, according to proposed weightings. These indicators will be compared with Ellen MacArthur's circularity indicator (MCI), trying to provide extra information to this factor. The process explained above will also be carried out at the product level, adapting the indicators that are appropriate for this level.

Some of these indicators, such as the potential for disassembly, will be difficult to calculate if it is not done on a specific building and it is not analysed where it is placed within the building and within which system. Therefore, it will be difficult to establish a form of calculation that does not involve the use of actual building assumptions so as not to incur unrealistic future assumptions. For example, an element may be designed to be dismantled for maintenance, replacement, or end of life but, if it is finally placed behind a building system that does not allow access to its dismantling or a wet construction layer, this element will end up being non removable. It will have a potential for demountability but it will not be in accordance with the final design result of the solution. Therefore, such future hypotheses will be useful if a concrete analysis of the construction solution is carried out within the building; it will not make sense to associate a factor to the product alone. These and other questions will arise during the analysis and methodological solutions will be provided on how to calculate or measure them.

This approach and indicators may change according to the development of the project and the revision of the State of Art of Circularity throughout these 3 years, created in the report *D6.5 - Circular Construction Guide*, which will be published in May 2027, and agreed with the rest of partners and external stakeholders. This analysis aims to provide harmonisation in the method of conducting circularity assessments, an increase in the amount of data monitored on real buildings, a methodology on the creation of assessment scenarios and, therefore, some final recommendations for the implementation of these analyses in future policies or public tenders. Moreover, trying to demonstrate that circularity, if thought from the beginning and in conjunction with the value chain, should not always translate into higher upfront costs.

One of the evaluation frameworks we rely on is necessarily LEVEL(s), together with other references of recognised entities such as Ellen MacArthur & Arup or the national tool (mainly for adaptability and quality inputs) of Valencian Institute of Edification (IVE), among others reviewed. Based on this research, we have defined the outputs that we will calculate as well

as the necessary inputs to reach them and the sources that allow us to obtain them, always under European regulations or recognised standards in the sector. If feasible, the results obtained will be translated into graphics and communication understandable by different users with different levels of expertise to overcome these knowledge barriers and foster awareness and interest.

Symbiosis potential

For estimating the symbiosis potential, Synerplatform is to be used, a software that facilitates data exploitation, making it accessible and generating useful information for diagnosis. The treatment of the data allows a preliminary analysis of the global opportunities for valorising the resources within a specific the territory. In a nutshell, this software

- identifies waste groups by its relevance,
- indicates how many companies need or generate a certain resource or waste,
- geolocates companies on a map to envision the possible flows of materials, energy, and waste,
- and identifies companies with possible synergies or innovative shared solutions.

In this case, for each material of interest some valorisation routes will be coded, i.e. which processes, technologies and actors are needed and for which application(s) or site(s) they could be used. This coding for the materials of interest is usually based on inputs from academic research publications, previous European projects, interviews with providers of innovative technological solutions, expert interviews, and previous knowledge of Símbiosy. Moreover, the platform enables the use of estimated datapoints when it lacks those inputs for a specific study. Through a dynamic analysis of the required inputs –mentioned in the next section- lists of regional actors and other relevant data related to each will be obtained -see outputs in the next section-, through a matchmaking process that will be done by the software. As a result, the symbiosis potential will be provided based on those outcomes, as an interpretation of the results of that process.

Figure 6.3 Outline of Synerplatform

The list of inputs required to develop the circularity assessment is shown below.

- Positions in the building (qualitative): This input is related to the geometric information that can be taken from the BIM model, with reference to the family (exterior or interior façade, pavement, fundings, etc.) to identify the system.
- Year of colocation (year): the year of installation or construction of the product /material is needed to get an idea of the material condition, the standard that was covered in that year and discover the durability of the product. Source: Material Passport.
- Composition of the product, per material (% of material per kg of product): The source will be the Digital Product Passports. This input is important to discover if there is a pure material or mixed and the type of union: dry, binders, adhesives, sealants, etc. The next step will be to investigate the actual existence of technology to separate the product into pure materials to enable recycling.
- Recycled content of each Product/material (% of recycled content in the total mass): Its usual source is the Digital Product Passport, Material Passport or databases with sector data. In this case, this recycled content will be measured during the production of the materials inside the consortium. For the external materials, suppliers will be asked to provide us with the recycled content documentation.
- Origin and suppliers of the materials (qualitative): Qualitative indicator that will contain the information about where the material comes from (including if it comes from another building) and which is its supplier/s. This information is comprehended in the Material Passport.
- Location of CDW treatment plants (locations): geolocation of CDW treatment plants in Catalonia to be assessed as potential sources of materials to be reused. This helps assessing the economic feasibility of obtaining these materials.

- Current condition of the material (qualitative): Qualitative indicator, which can bring information related to its possibility to reuse the product in other interventions or derivate to recycling, the need for maintenance to extend the lifespan or its substitution. It would be in the Digital Product Passport.
- Actual flow of territorial waste management of recycling (the quantity in kg of waste recycled in Catalonia). Source: Waste Catalan Agency
- Actual flow of territorial waste management of reusing (the quantity in kg of waste reused in Catalonia). Source: Waste Catalan Agency, the existent marketplaces or other platforms and statistics from literature review.
- Existent marketplaces (quantity): This input is related to the number of marketplaces in Catalonia and Brussels region, the prices and the possibilities within the project (incorporated material plus provide material to the platform). This will be sourced by questionnaires and internal search.
- Ease of separation of product components: Possibility and methods of separation (qualitative) + quantity of pure material that can be separated respect the total mixed material (kg/kg).
- Building sites on going of consortium partners (locations): The idea is to find sites & industries for reusing elements from CDW and the excess of materials fabricated. The first step is to find sites of the consortium partners (COM, INC, HOL), if not possible, external stakeholders will be consulted for developers contact.
- Life Cycle Global Warming Potential: LCA will be provided inside the consortium by ITeC in the unit of kg CO₂ equivalents per square meter per year (kg CO₂ eq./m²/year).
- Bill of quantities, materials (units and kg/m²): This information is comprehended in the Digital Product Passport.
- Construction waste type & Demolition waste type (code): A code from material list characterization was validated in WP1 from LEER European Codes and Spanish standard.
- Construction & Demolition waste quantity (kg/m²): From BIM model of the Digital Twin, we will monitor demos real data of the kg of each type of waste per m² constructed floor area. Comparison with LEVEL(s) statistics data in 2.2 Construction and demolition waste.
- Architecture: Detailed constructive solutions & plans: From BIM model
- Architecture: Hypothesis for adaptability: These hypotheses are validated in WP4 and transferred to plans and guides.
- Maintenance for each material: Quantity of materials incorporated for maintenance of a product and each frequency. It is supposed that Digital Twin will enable us to get this input.
- Hypothetical materials durability - service life (years): Its usual sources are RCP from EPD, specific manufacturer info included in Digital Product Passport. The directly output related is Cost per service life = (Initial cost + Maintenance costs + Replacement costs) / Estimated service life.

6.2.1 Output obtained

Below is the list of outputs that will emerge from the development of the required circularity assessment. All these outputs will be compared with a baseline building with conventional solutions to check the improvement of the constructed demo within the project. In addition, these results will be calculated for each stage of the building's life cycle (if applicable) and then summed to obtain the final result.

- Quantity of solutions in the building with circularity potential (dismountability): % kg /kg.
- Quantity of inert/ hazardous waste: % kg/m².
- Quantity of materials that close the loop (recycled content or renewable): % kg/m².
- Quantity of recyclability (different quality of waste, different recyclability): % kg/m² of recyclability and % kg/m² of under-recycling. It is useful because it relates waste and its circularity potential.
- Materials with valorisation potential (qualitative): materials developed within the project and found in CDW sites that have the possibility of being separated into pure materials or components and have actual value chain to recycle or reuse. Generalization with other products on the market.
- Qualitative data of adaptability/deconstruction from R10 tool: Qualitative indicator which will be weighted.
- Quantity of adaptability: % m² of its total construction surface. This indicator checks the percentage of buildings that can be adapted.
- MCI (material circular indicator): It is a factor developed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation and it will be considered to validate it.
- Cost per service life: (Initial cost + Maintenance costs + Replacement costs) / Estimated service life- (euro/year m²). It brings the economic aspect of circularity.
- Estimated Service life of the RECONSTRUCT material (years): To check the lifespan of the material developed and its reusing possibilities.
- List of recycling technologies (qualitative): benchmark of technologies required to reuse the materials in for new purposes as to assess their symbiosis potential.
- Markets for recycled products (qualitative): assessment of applications for each material with valorisation potential.
- Companies involved in the valorisation proces (qualitative): selection of companies that already have or could potentially develop/implement technologies for material valorisation, as well as participate in the value chain of the recycled product. It will include recyclers, manufacturers and suppliers.
- Maps of the reused materials (pictures): images of actors involved on the valorisation of each material selected value-chain. these will be obtained through Synerplatform.

7 Social impact assessment

7.1 Description

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), one of the main pillars of sustainability analysis considered in the project, depends on the guidelines and framework proposed by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2019). The UNEP guidelines provide an overall understanding of the key elements associated with assessing the social and socio-economic impacts of a product across its life cycle, from cradle to grave. Similar to environmental (LCA) and economic (LCC) assessment, UNEP suggests that S-LCA follows the four-step iterative approach: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation. However, the S-LCA emphasised by UNEP focuses on measuring social and socio-economic impacts at the product level. Therefore, the assessment is conducted to measure the impacts at the product level and then is aggregated for the complete building. Also, the indicators discussed in the report primarily focus on the whole life cycle social and socio-economic impacts at the building material (product) level.

As suggested by UNEP, the S-LCA of the products depends on the geographical locations and is observed in five stakeholder categories. The categories include 'stakeholder', 'worker', 'consumer', 'local community', 'society', and 'value chain actors excluding consumer'. Although more flexibilities are given to expand and change the stakeholder categories and their sub-category groups, this report primarily focuses on the listed stakeholder categories. Further analysis as the project progresses may lead to a minor redefinition of the current list.

The report consists of 11 impact indicators spanned across five stakeholder categories: working time, availability of resources, skills, training, and education provided to stakeholders, hazardousness levels, employment opportunities depending on gender, and other social factors like traffic, pollution, congestion, and local employment. Besides, technology development is one of the predominant categories in the UNEP's impact categories, which is also the critical pillar of the RECONSTRUCT. Technology development is generally valued by considering various factors like availability, adaptability, usability, cost, threat, integration, security, and privacy. Coupling these factors with social dimensions, the indicators, including data availability, quality, granularity, security, and automation level within the whole technological system, are also measured in the proposed approach.

While accounting for the data sources, the main sources of information broadly prescribed in the literature is considered. It includes the use of Internal and external databases like generic databases, manufacturer-specific product EPDs, and GIS data. However, in case of missing information in these prescribed databases for any of the indicators proposed in this report, the project will aim to gather the data by directly involving internal and external stakeholders, interviews, or surveys.

7.1.1 State of the art

An overview of similar S-LCA assessments available on the market, as well as their application and limitations, is discussed in D6.1 SI & Circular Construction.

7.1.2 Strengths and weaknesses

Strengths:

- The use of multiple stakeholder dimensions associated with S-LCA provides a holistic approach to understanding the needs of society, measuring the impacts, and developing comprehensive solutions. The social innovation, driven by new and creative solutions, would be achieved by adopting the proposed UNEP guided S-LCA approach.
- Integrating social dimensions into life cycle thinking aims to integrate the perspective of multiple stakeholders like local communities, workers, society, end users and value chain members. This drives innovation by solving new problems and providing a coherent vision enabling sustainable solutions.

Weaknesses:

- Since social assessment depends on various sources of information, the inconsistencies and lack of granularity in the dataset hinder its application.
- The use of qualitative assessment in measuring some of the S-LCA indicators increases the uniqueness of each dataset, thus making the process time-consuming and the analysis challenging to compare and measure.
- The literature has limited evidence on the application of S-LCA methodology within the context of the built environment. So, a comprehensive evaluation of indicators with subjective judgements increases the time and complexity of the process.
- Since the social and socio-economic impacts differ with geographical locations, the level of data generalisability is low. This leads to gathering a large amount of data for each assessment. Thus, the data management, unless held automatically, will consume more time and human resources. So, the lack of digital tools hinders the wide-scale application of the S-LCA.

7.2 Partner's methodology

The S-LCA proposed in the project follows a step-by-step approach with some iterations. Since the S-LCA depends on diverse indicators, each indicator follows a different approach in gathering inputs, processing the information, and presenting the results. So, this section will provide an overview of the S-LCA process, highlighting the changes expected in each step. The steps are as follows:

Step 1:

A narrative literature study is conducted to explore the application of the S-LCA approach within the built environment. The role of social impacts across the product life cycle, KPIs that decide the social impact of a product, application of existing methodologies, and type of inputs and outputs expected to meet the desired outcomes of S-LCA is explored. This helps to define the goal and scope of the S-LCA.

Step 2:

Utilising the information gathered from the literature review, validated in internal workshops with demo involved stakeholders, the predominant indicators impacting the outcomes of S-LCA are obtained. These impact indicators are clustered to align with stakeholder sub-categories and stakeholder categories highlighted by UNEP, adapted to the local clusters. The social and socio-economic impacts highlighted by UNEP are multi-dimensional. So, the guidelines suggest to the assessor that one stakeholder category can be affected by multiple impact categories, and one impact category can relate to multiple stakeholder categories. Therefore, the selected impact and stakeholder categories are listed in the table 7-1 here below, presenting their relationship. This will be used for assessment and validation purposes at each of the cluster levels.

S-LCA indicator (named)	Stakeholder sub-category from UNEP	Stakeholder category from UNEP
Working time (classified according to the gender)	Working hours	Worker
	Equal opportunities	Worker
Availability of resources to treat C&DW	Access to material resources	Local community
Skills/training/education to deal with C&DW materials	Access to immaterial resources	Local community
Level of C&DW hazardousness affecting the health and safety of workers	Health and Safety	Worker

Location of C&DW treatment units	Safe and healthy living conditions	Local community
	Local employment	Local community
	Contribution to economic development	Local community
Employment opportunities based on gender	Equal opportunities	Worker
Data security – database type and accessibility levels to gather information about a product	Respect of intellectual property rights	Value chain actors excluding consumers
Secondary product specifications – quantity and quality of data	Technology development	Society
Level of human intervention associated with developing and managing C&DW information within the CE-RECONSTRUCT context	Technology development	Society
	Access to immaterial resources	Local community
Data transparency - depending on the database type and information availability and how generalisable the collected data is for other scenarios	Transparency	Consumer
Involvement of external stakeholders communicated across the project life cycle	Feedback mechanism	Consumer
	Supplier relationships	Value chain actors excluding consumers
	Community engagement	Local community

Figure 7.1 Stakeholder category and its relationship with sub-categories with the RECONSTRUCT

Step 3:

Since multiple KPIs decide the social impact of the product (UNEP, 2019), the desired inputs, estimation process, and expected outputs are decided in this step. This step allows the assessor to decide on the type of data required for the analysis, the type of databases, the availability of information to conduct the analysis, and other external factors are examined in this step.

There is no even unit of measurement for social indicators, so it may be quantitative, qualitative, or semi-qualitative. So, a defined scoring or ranking approach will be decided in this step to ensure a high level of uniformity is obtained in presenting the S-LCA results. This helps to overcome the limitations of the current approach because of high qualitative data. Besides, ensuring uniformity in presenting the results will help the assessor integrate the analysis with other assessments like LCA, LCC, and circularity levels and support optimisation of materials accounting all these sustainability dimensions.

Step 4:

The final step involves evaluating impacts, measuring the indicators, and validating the results using internal and external stakeholders. The evaluation of impacts will be unique for each indicator, and the results will also be communicated accordingly. The proposed steps are flexible, so any changes incorporated before the final assessment will be reflected across the overall assessment process.

The type of inputs and outputs, sources of information and proposed measurement units will decide the flow of the S-LCA process. Hence, if necessary, the methodology defined in this report will be updated as the project progresses.

7.2.1 Input(s) required and Output(s) obtained

The input list is developed by aligning with UNEP's guidelines and framework on S-LCA indicators. Each input was selected based on its level of importance and appropriateness to the context of circular economy in the built environment.

- Working hours: The time spent on dealing with a specific task plays a vital role from the social sustainability perspective. It is considered to decide the impact on the stakeholder category 'workers'. The input data, benchmarked at hours/m² is gathered from BCCA and ITeC databases to obtain the overall working hours of a product.
- Type of resources required to deal with C&DW materials: Although reusing and recycling C&DW materials and enhancing the use of secondary products is environmentally sustainable, the use of resources, their type, time, and cost is vital to understanding the social dimension of the products. Thus, the type and quantity of resources (material/equipment/technologies) used to achieve the circularity levels are assessed.
- Type of training/education, number of training/education hours, and cost of training/education provided to stakeholders: Despite the materialistic resources, non-material resources like manpower and specialised skills to deal with materials

widely play an important role across the product life cycle (UNEP, 2019). So, the role of human resources, the type of training provided to each stakeholder, and its associated time and cost are assessed in this report within the S-LCA dimension.

- Hazardousness levels of C&DW: As highlighted in the UNEP guidelines, the health and safety of each stakeholder play a vital role in deciding the level of social sustainability. Hence, preventive measures should be taken to deal with construction materials that may have a certain degree of hazardous substances. These factors are assessed by gathering data about hazardousness via the ITeC LCA database and the European Waste Catalogue. The outputs are categorised as non-hazardous and hazardous materials, which allows the stakeholders to undergo appropriate measures.
- Location of C&DW treatment units (regional/national/international) with latitude and longitude and distance between construction/demolition site and C&DW treatment units: the geographical locations of waste treatment units are collected to assess the pollution, traffic congestion, and employment opportunities within a specific region. The latitude and longitude values are obtained as outputs via the GIS maps to assess the above-mentioned impacts.
- Gender type coupled with employment hierarchy: Equal opportunities, being one of the primary sub-categories within UNEP, talks about gender and employment levels across the life-cycle stages. So, these dimensions are assessed by having direct observation or interviews with the stakeholders involved from product manufacturing till the end of life.
- Level of security within each database: Database type (raw data sources) and accessibility levels to gather information about product, database type (raw data sources) and accessibility levels to gather information about a product, quality and quantity of secondary product information/specifications, Level of automation associated with the system (E.g., manual/semi-automated/automated) coupled with other factors, and Information about the quality of database (which provides information on the transparency levels) – All these inputs are associated with the technology development sub-category within UNEP framework. Since the technology development is assessed based on various factors like data availability, usability, security, privacy and accessibility, these factors are integrated into the assessment.
- List of stakeholders, role and participation type, and level within the project: One of the important aspects of social sustainability is to ensure the engagement of the local community and transparent relationships with the value chain members. So, accounting for those two dimensions, the level of engagement of each stakeholder across the project life cycle is gathered.

8 Project Impact assessment

8.1 Description

The report has summarized the monitoring of specific aspects of the impact in the project. **Overall impact will be assessed within the project developed tools over the developed case studies (demo sites in Barcelona and Brussels regions).** The results will be assessed also helped with the RE10 tool, the Ellen MacArthur foundation tool, and Level(s) framework tool. The model will include assumptions and limitations established and discussed with the demo and cluster stakeholders and the results upscaled to simulate future impacts of the project.

8.1.1 State of the art

The Project Impact Assessment is a document that brings together and links software and results from many parts of WP5 and the RECONSTRUCT project. With input from so many different sources, it has an innovative structure that is difficult to find in the current state of the art.

The reference to S-LCA from a perspective that equals in dimension the LCC is revolutionary in the sense that factors the indicators that relate to the supply chain, including EDI, gender, social and working indicators to amalgamate factors found in the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Level(s) and RE10 tool approaches.

8.1.2 Strengths and weaknesses

The strengths of the approach are:

- Benchmark between the tools in the project RECONSTRUCT and the existing reference frameworks (ARUP, Level(s)).
- A holistic impact approach that enables an economic, social, and circularity assessment
- Impacts referred to specific referenced KPIs
- A variety of settings and models with multiple products and material passports
- Validation of results within and outside the consortium with the clusters

The weaknesses detected are:

- Lack of full adherence to the New European Bauhaus framework due to time and information constraints.
- Incomplete set of information is foreseeable for parts of the demonstration, and therefore impacts will have limitations.

8.2 Partner's methodology

The digitisation approach in RECONSTRUCT allows a multisource RDF enable data feed to assess and evaluate construction impact from different standpoints and with a flexible factor weighing. A series of Multicriteria Decision Making Approaches will be used in *T3.5 - Development of the interface for RECONSTRUCT's digital ecosystem* to discern the best way of evaluating within the RECONSTRUCT tool ecosystem, that will enable gaining a symbiosis potential from products and elements reclaimed, recycled, and repurposed from a neighbouring area determined by GIS and based on partners' available platforms (SYM). The type of MCDM approach that will be selected for the analysis depends on the granularity and fuzziness of the inputs received for assessment.

The strategy bases upon semantic-web technologies applied to circular construction, an approach that has not been developed until now. The digitisation bases on the products and materials from *WP2 - Circular construction materials & components* that are realised into material, products and building passports that parallelly allow integration of factors that otherwise would make BIM models and digital twin solutions data intensive and slow in processing.

The complete integration of the developed tools and technical items in the project will be demonstrated with the BIM and related information in the Barcelona and Brussels sites and tested with two additional BIM models generated ad hoc by the partners, namely the NetZero Innovation Industrial Cluster (TEE).

8.2.1 Input required

The global impact assessment will be primarily based on the rest of tasks in the WP5 and the WP3. WP3 will provide information and tools related to the materials, products and building passports to be applied to the project demos.

Major inputs:

- Methodology from *WP5 - Monitoring and assessment of impacts* tasks: *5.2 - Life Cycle Assessment & Life Cycle Costing*, *5.3 - Circularity Assessment & Symbiosis potential* and *5.4 - Social Impact Assessment*, as listed in the Paragraph 4.1 of this document.
- Assessment of clusters to generate the uptake scenarios.
- Workshops with stakeholders to assess KPIs and validate the results of the MCDA.

8.2.2 Output obtained

The major outputs obtained in the task will be a comparison of the assessments for the demo sites with three different frameworks, as mentioned above in this chapter. The RECONSTRUCT tools will produce a set of environmental, economic, circularity and social impacts with validated and cluster relevant.

The other two frameworks to base upon will relate to the Ellen MacArthur and Level(s) to provide a European and international benchmark. The MCDA will be simulated within the cluster level, based on different uptake scenarios and number of buildings susceptible to be part of the RECONSTRUCT approach.

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

9 Conclusions

The assessments in WP5 will provide a clear understanding of the impact of the RECONSTRUCT demos, the circularity of building elements, and the sustainability of building materials. To ensure replicability and comparability with other documents developed with the same guidelines, it is important to adhere to the European frameworks. Improving the efficiency of the calculation method for future assessments requires evaluating the entire life cycle and assessing both initial estimates and the actual as-built situation.

9.1 Holistic management of project assessments

To draw up these documents, data must be obtained on the materials used, their production process, and the industrial process for producing building elements. It then requires data on the building, from the BIM design to the construction on site, and then on to the use phase and the very important phase for RECONSTRUCT's objectives, disassembly, and end-of-life.

It is crucial to understand how to handle the large volume of data required. An analysis of the necessary data, including possible sources, units of measurement, and calculation methods, is needed for each assessment. Standardising the starting inputs according to common guidelines is essential for assessments that require the same input.

To ensure homogeneity and comparability of data across various project assessments, it is important to consistently identify common inputs and name them. Additionally, the same sources and units of measurement should be used. This ensures that the data in different project assessments is uniform and can be compared easily. It also allows for easy exchange of information if needed. Compliance with European frameworks, especially for units of measurement and calculation methods used for each indicator, is also necessary.

Assesment	Partner	Input required	Unit of measurement	Usual sources	Input Typology
LCA	ITEC	Use phase energy demand	kWh/y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Use phase energy demand cooling	kWh/y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Use phase energy demand heating	kWh/y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Non-renewable energy during use	kWh/y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Use Emissions	tCO2eq/y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Material lifecycle span	y	BEDEC, EPD	Use
LCA	ITEC	Waste Disposal Emissions	kgCO2eq/kg	BEDEC, EPD	Demolition
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Positions in the building & year of colocation	Geometric, year	BIM model	Material Production /
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Characteristics of each material: composition of the product	% per kg	Digital Product Passport	Material Production
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Characteristics of each material: recycled content	% (kg/kg)	Digital Product Passport	Material Production
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Characteristics of each material: origin and suppliers of the materials	Qualitative	Digital Product Passport	Material Production
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Characteristics of each material: current condition of the material	Qualitative	Digital Product Passport	Construction
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Waste: actual flow of waste management	kg of waste for recycling	Waste Catalan Agency	Demolition
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Waste: actual flow of waste management	kg of material for reused in the market	Waste Catalan Agency & other LR	Construction/ demolit
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Waste: existent marketplaces	nº of marketplaces at a Bcn/Bxl level	LR of Marketplaces	Demolition
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Waste: ease of separation of product component	methods of separation, kg of virgin material / kg of mixed material	Material passport	Demolition
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Waste: building sites on going for reusing elements	Sites & developer contact	Consortium partners (COM, INC, HOL, GEP)	Demolition
CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT	SOD	Life cycle Global Warming Potential	kg CO2 equivalents per square metre per year (kg CO2 eq./m2/yr)	BEDEC, EPD	Environmental Impact

Figure 9.1 – List of the inputs needed for each assessment

It is important to note that some outputs of one document may be required inputs for another. For instance, the circularity assessment may require an LCA output. By adhering to this shared language established in the project's initial stages, information exchange can be facilitated, and a comprehensive project overview can be achieved.

9.2 T5.1 – Impact assessment plan and continuous monitoring : next steps

During phase 1 of the project, the identification of inputs and outputs for the assessments was initiated. This process aided in comprehending the requirements of each document and establishing the structure for the assessments.

The second phase of task 5.1 commences from the presentation of the D5.1 impact monitoring plan in month 9 and concludes with the commencement of the assessment drafting in month 30. During this phase, the work will be carried out to homologate the inputs, considering the requirements of various calculation methods and frameworks.

The assessments presented in this document gather information on materials, elements, and demo buildings from activities carried out in other WPs, specifically WP2, WP3, and WP4. It is crucial to connect with these activities to collect information.

During phase 2 of Task 5.1, partners will hold regular meetings to update each other on developments in other work packages. These meetings will help to determine whether and how to update the predictions made in this deliverable and the structure of the assessments. Integration into BIM models, RDF based data sets and GIS solutions are important.

The inputs and structure of the assessments will be presented, discussed, and validated with external stakeholders during the initial stages of the WP. This will allow the work to be validated through a co-design process involving external stakeholders and the clusters of the two demos, groups of companies, and experts interested in the project topics, both internal and external to RECONSTRUCT.

10 References

- ⁱ Dodd, N., Donatello, S., & Cordella, M. (2021, January 01). Level(s) - A common EU framework of core sustainability indicators for office and residential buildings User Manual 1: Introduction to the Level(s) common framework (Publication version 1.1).
- ⁱⁱ European Union. (2023). Circular Economy - Introducing Levels. Retrieved from [https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels/introducing-levels_en]
- ⁱⁱⁱ Five Agency. (2023). RE10. Retrieved from [<https://www.five.es/project/re10/>]
- ^{iv} Goddin, J., Marshall, K., Pereira, A., Tuppen, C., Herrmann, S., Jones, S., ... Sullens, W. (2019, December 9). Circularity Indicators: An Approach to Measuring Circularity, Methodology. [10.13140/RG.2.2.29213.84962]
- ^v Five Agency. (2023). RE10 Circularidad. Retrieved from [<https://productos.five.es/producto/re10-circularidad>]
- ^{vi} Andrews, E., Barthel, L.-P., Norris, C., Ciroth, A., Cucuzzella, C., Gensch, C.-O., ... Weidema, B. (2009). Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products. ISBN: 978-92-807-3021-0
- ^{vii} European Committee for Standardization (CEN). (2006). EN 14040: Environmental management—Life cycle assessment—Principles and framework.
- ^{viii} European Committee for Standardization (CEN). (2006). EN 14044: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines.
- ^{ix} European Committee for Standardization (CEN). (2019). EN 15804:2012+A2:2019 Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products.
- ^x European Committee for Standardization (CEN). (2011). EN 15978:2011 Sustainability of construction works – Assessment of environmental performance of buildings – Calculation method.
- ^{xi} European Committee for Standardization (CEN). (2015). EN 16627:2015 Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of economic performance of buildings - Calculation methods.
- ^{xii} Ramboll, BPIE, & KU Leuven. (2023). Support Study for the Development of the Roadmap for the Reduction of Whole Life Carbon of Buildings. Retrieved from <https://c.ramboll.com/whole-life-carbon-reduction>
- ^{xiii} European Union. (2010). Directive EU/2010/31 [Revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)]
- ^{xiv} Circle Economy. (2020). The Circularity Gap Report 2020
- ^{xv} Roh, S. J. (2020). EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol and Best Practice Examples. Magazine of RCR, 15(2), 11-16
- ^{xvi} Breen, M., Reus, L., Milovanovic, B., Callinan, G., Dvořáková, P., Cromwijk, J., & Poort, C. (2023). Developing a task-based qualification framework for circular skills in construction and its application in training plans (for trainers and SMEs). Zenodo. Available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10417173> (accessed on 30, 1st, 2024)
- ^{xvii} SCALER Project. (2023). Reports. Retrieved from [<https://www.scalerproject.eu/resources/reports>]

